

CRESCENT Tsunami Benchmark (TTPV1 and TTPV2): 3D fully coupled earthquake dynamic rupture and tsunami benchmarks with varying bathymetric complexity

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The Tsunami Problem Version (TTPV) 1

Spontaneous 3D earthquake dynamic rupture on a 15 degree dipping thrust fault reaching the Earth's surface (i.e., the seafloor) with a 1 km thick uniform water layer atop.

The Tsunami Problem Version (TTPV) 2

Spontaneous 3D earthquake dynamic rupture on a 15 degree dipping thrust fault reaching the seafloor. A water layer with variable depth is atop the elastic Earth, with 3 km water depth on the seaward side, sloping to shallow depth (~ 50 m) landwards.

A few notes:

- This is the first joint CRESCENT & SCEC/USGS and first fully coupled earthquake dynamic rupture and tsunami community code verification benchmark exercise. Comments can be directed to fkutschera@ucsd.edu and agabriel@ucsd.edu.
- While this benchmark setup is closely related to TPV36, model configurations and sign conventions differ. Modelers are asked to carefully check this benchmark description.
- Two different model geometries are needed to run the fully coupled benchmarks TTPV1 and TTPV2, respectively. The governing earthquake dynamic rupture initial conditions and fault geometry remain the same for both problems.

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1 Overview and model description

The two joint CRESCENT & SCEC/USGS benchmark problems TTPV1 and TTPV2 extend the SCEC/USGS dynamic rupture benchmark “The Problem Version 36” (TPV36, https://strike.scec.org/cvws/download/TPV36_37_Description_v12.pdf; last access May 12, 2025), a 3D shallowly dipping thrust faulting dynamic rupture problem, which includes surface rupture. “The Tsunami Problem Version 1” (TTPV1) and “The Tsunami Problem Version 2” (TTPV2) use the same fault geometry, nucleation mechanism, governing friction law, material properties, and initial stress conditions. The differences are an added water layer and, in TTPV2, varying seafloor bathymetry, to model fully coupled earthquake and tsunami generation dynamics. Both simulations also include acoustic wave propagation within the ocean.

1.1 Submission and modeling results

We ask all modelers to upload their results to <https://det-uploader.cascadiaquakes.org>. A single *.zip* file can be uploaded as long as the naming conventions are followed and individual file sizes are less than ~ 300 MB. Once an account has been created and results uploaded, the results can be viewed at <https://det.cascadiaquakes.org>.

1.2 Continuum problem

Fully coupled modeling of seismic waves, ocean acoustic waves, and tsunamis was introduced by [Maeda and Furumura \(2013\)](#) using a Lagrangian-type formulation of the governing equations. Soon after, [Lotto and Dunham \(2015\)](#) introduced an alternative Eulerian approach. Research in this area has continued for the past decade, with a variety of approaches for coupled earthquake-tsunami modeling compared by [Abrahams et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Someya et al. \(2024\)](#), with the latter providing formulations that most thoroughly account for the effects of gravity. For TTPV1 and TTPV2, we use the fully coupled method of [Lotto and Dunham \(2015\)](#), which combines the elastic wave equation in the solid Earth (Section 1.2.2) with the linearized equations of motion governing small perturbations of a compressible ocean (Section 1.2.3) about a rest state in hydrostatic equilibrium. Some effects of gravity, which affect tsunami dispersion over long propagation distances, are neglected. The initial 2D implementations by [Lotto and Dunham \(2015\)](#) and [Wilson and Ma \(2021\)](#) were extended to 3D by [Krenz et al. \(2021\)](#). The ocean and solid are coupled by enforcing continuity of the normal velocity and traction components of stress across the seafloor interface ([Abrahams et al., 2023](#)).

1.2.1 3D coordinate system

The coordinate system (E-W, N-S, Up-Down; that is x, y, z with z pointing up) chosen here **differs from SCEC/USGS TPV36**, where y pointed down. Here, as shown in Fig. 1, x increases from left to right, y increases from front to back, and z increases from the seafloor to the sea surface and decreases from the seafloor downwards. In TTPV1, $z = 0$ marks the seafloor, $z > 0$ is the water layer, $z < 0$ is the elastic medium, while TTPV2 features a depth-dependent bathymetry (with $z = 0$ where the fault reaches the seafloor). The trace of the fault along the seafloor is at $x = 0$.

1.2.2 Earth

We consider a semi-infinite half-space, where the Earth is considered as homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic medium. The deformation of the medium is governed by the momentum balance, with six stress components ($\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{xy}, \sigma_{xz}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{yz}, \sigma_{zz}$), three displacement components (u_x, u_y, u_z), and three velocity components (v_x, v_y, v_z). Using index notation ($i, j \in \{x, y, z\}$) and Einstein summation convention, we get the equation of motion

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \rho g \delta_{iz}, \quad (1)$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, ρ is the solid density, and g is the gravitational acceleration. Displacements and strains are defined with respect to a prestressed reference configuration in equilibrium with gravity, satisfying

$$0 = \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^0}{\partial x_j} - \rho g \delta_{iz}, \quad (2)$$

where σ_{ij}^0 is the prestress. Deformation about the reference configuration is linear elastic, with Hooke's law relating stress changes to strains (here in terms of displacement) by

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^0 + \lambda \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right). \quad (3)$$

Here, μ, λ are the isotropic, elastic moduli (Section 2). This benchmark can be solved using either displacements or velocities as unknowns. For completeness, we provide both. The displacement formulation is obtained by subtracting Eq. 2 from Eq. 1 and then inserting Eq. 3. The difference between the initial and perturbed density is neglected on the right side. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\lambda \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \lambda \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} + \mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_j}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In the velocity-stress formulation of the elastodynamic equations, the order of the partial differential equation is reduced, as:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial t} - \lambda \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} - \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial x_j} = 0. \quad (6)$$

1.2.3 Ocean

For the continuum problem governing the ocean dynamics, we follow [Krenz et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Abrahams et al. \(2023\)](#), who extended the work of [Lotto and Dunham \(2015\)](#) and

Wilson and Ma (2021) from 2D to 3D. Starting from an Eulerian (spatial) description, we consider a compressible, inviscid ocean with perturbations around the hydrostatic rest state. Here, the unperturbed sea surface is at $z = H$, where H is the height of the ocean at rest, while the perturbed ocean surface is at $z = H + \eta(x, y, t)$ with η as the vertical displacement of the sea surface. Consequently, by combining conservation of mass (continuity equation) with a linearized equation of state, we get

$$\frac{\partial p'}{\partial t} + K \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} = 0, \quad (7)$$

where K is the bulk modulus and the pressure $p(x, y, z, t) = p_0(z) + p'(x, y, z, t)$ is the sum of the initial hydrostatic pressure $p_0(z)$ and the pressure perturbation $p'(x, y, z, t)$ (Lotto and Dunham, 2015). Subsequently, the conservation of momentum yields

$$\rho \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (8)$$

where ρ is the ocean density (not to be confused with the solid density that is also denoted by ρ). The linearized equations should include additional terms on the right hand sides of Eqs. 7, 8, but for this benchmark these are set to zero, as they are of much smaller magnitude than the retained terms on the left hand side (Lotto and Dunham, 2015). The governing equations in the ocean are therefore the equations of linear acoustics.

Since the tsunami amplitude $|\eta|$ is much smaller than the horizontal wavelength and water depth, we use the following linearized free surface boundary condition at the sea surface:

$$p'(x, y, H, t) = \rho g \eta. \quad (9)$$

The system of equations is closed through the linearized kinematic condition for the sea surface:

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = v_z(x, y, H, t). \quad (10)$$

1.2.4 Interface conditions at the seafloor

The seafloor has a unit normal, pointing from the solid into the ocean, with component n_i . We use superscripts $+$ and $-$ to denote fields evaluated on the ocean side and solid side of the seafloor, respectively. The interface conditions (e.g., Dahlen and Tromp, 1999) at the seafloor are continuity of the normal velocity,

$$v_i^+ n_i = v_i^- n_i, \quad (11)$$

and continuity of the traction components of stress,

$$-p' n_i = n_j (\sigma_{ji} - \sigma_{ji}^0). \quad (12)$$

The latter condition sets the shear tractions on the solid side of the seafloor to zero, consistent with the ocean being inviscid, as well as balancing the change in solid side normal traction with the change in pressure on the ocean side. We remark that an additional term proportional to the density difference between the ocean and solid (Dahlen and Tromp, 1999) has been neglected in Eq. 12. This term is negligible compared to the retained terms.

1.3 Model geometry

In TTPV1 and TTPV2, the fault plane is embedded within a homogeneous elastic medium (i.e., Earth) and dips at 15 degrees towards the East (in positive x-direction).

The rectangular fault is a planar thrust fault, measuring 30 km along-strike and 28 km down-dip. The fault reaches the seafloor. The fault trace is located at $x = 0$ and at depth $z = 0$ for TTPV1 and TTPV2. We choose a coordinate system with the fault dipping 15 degrees in positive x-direction (landward). Thus, the fault plane's spatial coordinates are:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= |z| / (\tan 15^\circ) \\ -15 \text{ km} &\leq y \leq 15 \text{ km} \\ -(28 \text{ km}) \cdot (\sin 15^\circ) &\leq z \leq -0 \text{ km} \end{aligned}$$

The hypocenter is located in the center of the fault along-strike (at $y = 0$), and 18000 m down-dip. The exact hypocenter coordinates (x, y, z) are (17387.0 m, 0.0 m, -4658.0 m). We will compare the surface output (seafloor displacement and tsunami generation) across the area of $x \in [-100, 100]$ km and $y \in [-100, 100]$ km.

Figure 1: 3D model geometry of The Tsunami Benchmark Problem 1 (TTPV1). The rectangular, black shaded planar fault is embedded within an elastic medium (Earth) and reaches the seafloor. The acoustic medium (water layer) captures the ocean acoustic and ocean gravity (tsunami) waves.

1.3.1 The Tsunami Benchmark Problem 1 (TTPV1)

Fig. 1 shows the geometry of TTPV1. Here, a uniform water layer is added atop the elastic medium with a thickness of 1 km. The sea surface is at $z = 1000$ m and the seafloor is at a constant depth of $z = 0$ m. A side view of the model geometry for TTPV1 is shown in Fig. 2.

1.3.2 The Tsunami Benchmark Problem 2 (TTPV2)

For TTPV2, the sea surface level is constant at $z = 3000$ m. However, the underlying model geometry is more complex. While the fault geometry and fault coordinates remain the same, the bathymetry in this benchmark problem is variable. Seaward of the “trench” (the fault trace), a uniform water depth of 3 km atop the Earth is assumed. To the East of the trench, the seafloor slopes, following:

$$z_{\text{sf}} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } x < 0. \\ h [1 - \exp(-x/L)], & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where $h = 2950$ m is the maximum height change of the seafloor to the east, and $L = 10$ km being the horizontal length scale over which the ocean depth changes. The minimum depth of the water is approximately 50 m in the east.

Figure 2: Side views of the model geometries for TTPV1 (top) and TTPV2 (bottom). The 3D geometry of TTPV1 is depicted in Fig. 1, with a **1 km ocean** of uniform thickness atop the elastic medium. The geometry for TTPV2 differs, with a **3 km thick ocean** westwards (seaward) of the fault trace (trench). To the East of the trench (landward), the bathymetry is characterized by a **slope, with the water depth approaching 50 m** based on the function specified in Eq. 13.

1.4 Simulation time and resolution

On-fault resolution follows TPV36, where a 50 m node spacing was recommended. Modelers should choose an appropriate but computationally feasible spatial discretization of the water layer, depending on their code specifics and computational demands.

The simulation time for TTPV1 and TTPV2 is **4 minutes** each.

2 Material properties

Earth (elastic):

In TTPV1 and TTPV2, the Earth is considered as a homogeneous elastic medium, with the same parameters as used in TPV36:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Density } \rho &= 2670 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \\ \text{Pressure-wave velocity } v_p &= 6000 \text{ m s}^{-1} \\ \text{Shear-wave velocity } v_s &= 3464 \text{ m s}^{-1} \\ \text{(1st Lamé parameter } \lambda &= 32.04375936 \text{ GPa)} \\ \text{(2nd Lamé parameter } \mu &= 32.03812032 \text{ GPa)} \end{aligned}$$

Water (acoustic):

For the water layer placed atop the elastic medium we prescribe a uniform density of 1000 kg m^{-3} and an ocean acoustic wave speed of 1500 m s^{-1} (that is $K = 2.25 \text{ GPa}$).

3 Dynamic rupture model setup

3.1 Sign conventions

The signs chosen here **differ from SCEC/USGS TPV36**. In this benchmark, normal stress (σ_n) is negative in compression, consistent with the stress tensor being positive in tension. The shear traction along dip (τ_{dip}) is defined as positive (opposite to TPV36) when it acts to move the hanging wall upward and the footwall downward. The shear traction along strike (τ_{strike}) is defined as positive when it acts to cause right-lateral slip. The same sign conventions apply to slip velocity and slip.

Following the formulation by Day et al. (2005), the fault surface is denoted by Σ . This surface Σ has a (continuous) unit normal vector n_i , such that the traction vector is given by $t_i = \sigma_{ij}n_j$, and the shear traction is the tangential component of the traction, that is $\tau_i := t_i - (n_j t_j)n_i$.

We also use the notation $[[\cdot]]$ to denote the jump operator, defined as the difference in each respective quantity across the two sides of the fault interface Σ (i.e., the value on the positive side of the fault, toward which the unit normal points, minus the value on the opposite side). For example, the discontinuity in displacement across the fault is $[[u_i]]$.

3.2 Friction and fault strength

Here, we state the interface conditions on the fault. First, the fault is constrained against opening,

$$[[u_i]]n_i = 0, \quad (14)$$

and it follows from Newton's third law that the components of the stress tensor exerting tractions on the fault are continuous across the interface.

The shear traction is bounded by the fault (frictional, positive) strength τ_c via

$$||\boldsymbol{\tau}|| \leq \tau_c. \quad (15)$$

The time derivative of the discontinuity of the vector of tangential displacement yields the slip rate $[[V_i]] := [[\dot{u}_i]]$. The second part of the jump condition at Σ enforces that whenever there is slip across the fault (i.e., $\mathbf{V} \neq \mathbf{0}$), the shear resistance to sliding $-\boldsymbol{\tau}$ must exactly oppose the direction of slip rate and have a magnitude equal to the fault strength τ_c :

$$\tau_c \mathbf{V} - \boldsymbol{\tau} ||\mathbf{V}|| = 0. \quad (16)$$

In other words, this means that the slip rate and the shear traction are parallel, and that the slip rate must be zero whenever the magnitude of the shear traction is less than the fault strength (Day et al., 2005).

The fault strength τ_c for both TTPV1 and TTPV2 is determined using the same **linear slip-weakening (LSW) friction law** (e.g., Ida, 1972) with cohesion to model frictional yielding and dynamic slip evolution as applied in TPV36.

$$\tau_c = C_0 - \mu \cdot \min(0, \sigma_n). \quad (17)$$

Here, C_0 is the cohesion, even added even during forced rupture, and μ is the friction coefficient, which depends on the nucleation friction coefficient μ_{nuc} (Section 3.3) and the slip-weakening friction coefficient μ_{lsw} , given by the linear slip-weakening friction law,

$$\mu_{lsw}(S) = \mu_s - \frac{\mu_s - \mu_d}{D_c} \min(S, D_c), \quad (18)$$

which is a function of the accumulated fault slip $S(t) = \int_0^t ||\mathbf{V}|| dt$ at each point on the fault. Here, μ_{lsw} decreases linearly from the static friction coefficient (μ_s) to the dynamic friction coefficient (μ_d) over a characteristic slip-weakening distance (D_c). The parameter values are

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_s &= 0.575 \\ \mu_d &= 0.450 \\ D_c &= 0.18 \text{ m}. \end{aligned}$$

Cohesion is set up in the same way for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Cohesion varies as a function of depth, with down-dip distance w :

$$w = |z| / (\sin 15^\circ) \quad \text{for } z < 0. \quad (19)$$

The cohesion C_0 is:

$$C_0 = \begin{cases} (500 \text{ Pa m}^{-1}) \cdot (8000 \text{ m} - w) & \text{if } w \leq 8000 \text{ m} \\ 0 & \text{if } w > 8000 \text{ m} \end{cases}$$

As a result, for both TTPV1 and TTPV2 the cohesion at the trench is equal to $C_0 = 4 \text{ MPa}$.

3.3 Nucleation

The nucleation follows exactly TPV36 and is performed by forcing the fault to rupture within a circular zone surrounding the hypocenter. Forced rupture is achieved by artificially reducing the nucleation friction coefficient μ_{nuc} , beginning at a specified time $T(r)$ that depends on r , the radial distance from the hypocenter:

$$\mu_{nuc}(t, r) = \begin{cases} \mu_s, & t < T(r), \\ \mu_s - (\mu_s - \mu_d) \frac{t - T(r)}{t_0}, & T(r) \leq t < T(r) + t_0, \\ \mu_d, & t \geq T(r) + t_0. \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

The parameter t_0 specifies how long it takes for the nucleation friction coefficient to be artificially reduced from its static value μ_s to its dynamic value μ_d . So, the friction coefficient reaches its dynamic value at time $T(r) + t_0$. As in TPV36, we selected $t_0 = 0.5 \text{ s}$, and the time of forced rupture is defined to be

$$T(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{r}{0.7v_s} + \frac{0.081r_{crit}}{0.7v_s} \left(\frac{1}{1-(r/r_{crit})^2} - 1 \right) & \text{if } r < r_{crit} \\ 10^9 \text{ s} & \text{if } r \geq r_{crit} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where $r_{crit} = 4000 \text{ m}$ is the radius of the nucleation zone. At the hypocenter, $T = 0$. The value of T then increases with distance from the hypocenter, which creates an expanding circular region of forced rupture. This expansion of the forced rupture region is designed to transition smoothly into spontaneous rupture, such that the friction coefficient μ used to evaluate fault strength (Eq. 17) is given by:

$$\mu(t, S) = \min(\mu_{lsw}(S), \mu_{nuc}(t, r)) \quad (22)$$

This means that initially near the hypocenter, the forced rupture front expands at a speed of $0.7v_s$ (Fig. 3), where v_s is the shear wave velocity. This expansion speed gradually decreases (following Eq. 21) with increasing distance from the hypocenter, eventually reaching zero at r_{crit} . This gradual deceleration ensures that the spontaneous rupture overtakes the forced rupture smoothly, minimizing artifacts such as spurious oscillations.

Figure 3: Forced rupture speed v_r as a function of distance from hypocenter r , where $v_r = dr/dT$.

3.4 Initial stress assumptions

The initial normal stress ($\sigma_{n,ini}$) and initial shear stress along dip direction ($\tau_{dip,ini}$) on the fault follow TPV36, but modelers should be aware of the different sign convention used here (Section 3.1). The initial shear stress along strike direction ($\tau_{strike,ini}$) is equal to zero. Both $\sigma_{n,ini}$ and $\tau_{dip,ini}$ are proportional to distance down-dip (Eq. 19):

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{n,ini} &= (-4240 \text{ Pa m}^{-1}) \cdot w \\ \tau_{dip,ini} &= (2120 \text{ Pa m}^{-1}) \cdot w.\end{aligned}$$

The hypocenter for TTPV1 and TTPV2 lies 18 km down-dip, and so $w_{\max} = 18000$ m. Based on the formulas above, the initial normal and shear stress at the hypocenter are $\sigma_{n,ini} = -76.32$ MPa (negative in compression) and $\tau_{dip,ini} = 38.16$ MPa (along-dip; positive).

4 Off-fault stations

A **total of 102 off-fault receivers** will need to be placed in each simulation. For both TTPV1 and TTPV2, three sets of off-fault (that is, body) receivers are located **buried just beneath the seafloor (elastic), just above the seafloor (acoustic), and at the sea surface**. We build upon TPV36, extending their naming convention. The body receivers' horizontal coordinates (Fig. 4 and Tables 1, 2) remain the same for TTPV1 and TTPV2, but the vertical coordinates differ.

4.1 Elastic: seafloor

We ask the modelers to upload 34 (body) receivers placed at the seafloor in the elastic medium for each TTPV1 and TTPV2. The receiver output includes the three-component velocities and displacements over time, detailed in Tables 3, 4.

4.2 Acoustic: seafloor & sea surface

We ask the modelers to upload 68 (body) receivers placed at the seafloor & sea surface in the acoustic medium for each TTPV1 and TTPV2. Here, in addition to the three-component velocities and displacements, the modelers are asked to upload pressure signals, motivated by ocean bottom pressure sensors (OBPS). Specifically, for the off-fault receivers in the water (both at the seafloor and at the sea surface), the modelers are asked to add the Eulerian pressure perturbation p' as Column #8 to the off-fault time series for the receivers in the acoustic medium. The modelers are also asked to upload the Lagrangian pressure perturbation Δp (which adds to p' the pressure perturbation caused by advection of the fluid parcel through the background hydrostatic pressure gradient) as Column #9 to the off-fault time series for the receivers in the acoustic medium (Tables 3, 4). The Lagrangian pressure perturbation is the pressure perturbation that would be measured on an instrument that moves with the deforming seafloor.

4.3 Naming convention

With 102 off-fault receivers for each simulation, placed in different parts of the computational domain, we need a clear distinction of their names. Please use the following prefixes for the station names from Table 2:

- For body receivers placed at the **seafloor** in the **elastic** medium (Section 8.3.1):
el_sf_
 - Example: *el_sf_body-210st000.csv*
- For body receivers placed at the **seafloor** in the **acoustic** medium (Section 8.3.2):
ac_sf_
 - Example: *ac_sf_body-210st000.csv*
- For body receivers placed at the **sea surface** in the **acoustic** medium (Section 8.3.3):
ac_ss_
 - Example: *ac_ss_body-210st000.csv*

Figure 4: Horizontal coordinates of the off-fault receivers as used for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Each dot represents locations at different depths: sea surface (acoustic), seafloor (acoustic), and seafloor (elastic).

Table 1: Horizontal coordinates [km] of the body receivers. Here (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) , that is (Easting, Northing).

(-21.0, 0.0)	(-21.0, 10.0)	(-21.0, 20.0)
(-15.0, 0.0)	(-15.0, 10.0)	(-15.0, 20.0)
(-9.0, 0.0)	(-9.0, 10.0)	(-9.0, 20.0)
(-3.0, 0.0)	(-3.0, 10.0)	
(-1.0, 0.0)	(-1.0, 10.0)	
(1.0, 0.0)	(1.0, 10.0)	
(3.0, 0.0)	(3.0, 10.0)	
(9.0, 0.0)	(9.0, 10.0)	(9.0, 20.0)
(15.0, 0.0)	(15.0, 10.0)	
(21.0, 0.0)	(21.0, 10.0)	
(27.0, 0.0)	(27.0, 10.0)	(27.0, 20.0)
(33.0, 0.0)		
(39.0, 0.0)		
(45.0, 0.0)	(45.0, 10.0)	(45.0, 20.0)
(51.0, 0.0)		
(57.0, 0.0)		

Table 2: Off-fault (body) receivers for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Note that **each station name needs to have its own prefix (Section 4.3)**.

<i>Prefix + Station Name</i>	Location
body-210st000	-21.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-210st100	-21.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-210st200	-21.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 20.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-150st000	-15.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-150st100	-15.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-150st200	-15.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 20.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-090st000	-9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-090st100	-9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-090st200	-9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 20.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-030st000	-3.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-030st100	-3.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-010st000	-1.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body-010st100	-1.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body010st000	1.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body010st100	1.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body030st000	3.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body030st100	3.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body090st000	9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body090st100	9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body090st200	9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 20.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body150st000	15.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body150st100	15.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body210st000	21.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body210st100	21.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body270st000	27.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body270st100	27.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body270st200	27.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 20.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body330st000	33.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body390st000	39.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body450st000	45.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body510st000	51.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)
body570st000	57.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 0.0 km along strike (y-dir)

Table 3: Off-fault time series data fields for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Each time series file is an ASCII file that contains multiple data fields on each line.

¹Only for the off-fault receivers placed in the acoustic medium. Example implementation choices are stated in Sections 8.3.2, 8.3.3, and 8.4.

Field Name	Description, Units, and Sign Convention
t	Time (s).
x-disp	Horizontal displacement in x-direction, perpendicular to the fault strike (m).
x-vel	Horizontal velocity in x-direction, perpendicular to the fault strike (m s^{-1}).
y-disp	Horizontal displacement in y-direction, parallel to the fault strike (m).
y-vel	Horizontal velocity in y-direction, parallel to the fault strike (m s^{-1}).
z-disp	Vertical displacement in z-direction (m). Please ensure that uplift is positive and subsidence is negative. Note: for the acoustic medium, this corresponds to the sea surface height (η).
z-vel	Vertical velocity in z-direction (m s^{-1}).
pprime	Pressure perturbation (Eulerian) in the acoustic medium ¹ (Pa).
dp	Pressure perturbation (Lagrangian) in the acoustic medium ¹ (Pa).

Table 4: Off-fault time series file format for TTPV1 and TTPV2. The off-fault time series file consists of three sections.

File Section	Description
File Header	<p>A series of lines, each beginning with a <code>#</code> symbol, that identifies the file. The following information is required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmark problem (TTPV1 or TTPV2) • Author(s) • Date • Code • Code version • Node spacing or element size • Time integration method • Output time step size • Number of output time steps in file • Station location (x,y,z) • Pre- and post-processing (if applicable) • Descriptions of data columns • Anything else you think is relevant
Field List	<p>A single line, which lists the names of the data fields in column order, separated by spaces. It should be</p> <pre style="text-align: center;">t x-disp x-vel y-disp y-vel z-disp z-vel [pprime dp]</pre> <p>(all on one line). Please include p and dp only for receivers in the acoustic medium. The benchmark platform examines this line to check that your file contains the correct data fields.</p>
Time History	<p>A series of lines. Each line contains multiple numbers, which give the data values for a single time step. The lines must appear in order of increasing time.</p>

Here is an example of an off-fault time-series file. This is an invented file, not real modeling data.

```
# Example off-fault time-series file.
#
# This is the file header:
# problem = TTPV1
# author = Name Modeler
# date = 2025/01/27
# code = MyCode
# code_version = 1.2.0
# element_size (order) = 200 m (o4)
# time_integration = ADER
# output_time_step = 0.005
# number_output_time_steps = 2400
# location = 9.0 km off-fault (x-dir), 10.0 km along strike (y-dir), -0.0 km depth
# processing = None
# Column #1 = Time (s)
# Column #2 = horizontal displacement perpendicular to strike (x-dir) (m)
# Column #3 = horizontal velocity perpendicular to strike (x-dir) (m/s)
# Column #4 = horizontal displacement parallel to strike (y-dir) (m)
# Column #5 = horizontal velocity parallel to strike (y-dir)(m/s)
# Column #6 = vertical displacement (z-dir) (m)
# Column #7 = vertical velocity (z-dir) (m/s)
# If applicable:
#     Column #8 = pressure perturbation (Eulerian), acoustic medium (Pa)
#     Column #9 = pressure perturbation (Lagrangian), acoustic medium (Pa)
#
# The line below lists the names of the data fields:
t x-disp x-vel y-disp y-vel z-disp z-vel [pprime dp]
#
# Here is the time-series data.
# There should be multiple numbers on each line, but this page is not wide enough
# to show all numbers on a line, so we only show the first five.
0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 ...
5.000000E-03 -2.077270E-85 -2.575055E-83 -2.922774E-86 -3.623018E-84 ...
1.000000E-02 -1.622118E-82 -2.005817E-80 -1.387778E-83 -1.713249E-81 ...
1.500000E-02 -9.020043E-80 -1.114231E-77 -4.402893E-81 -5.424313E-79 ...
2.000000E-02 -1.201684E-77 -1.467704E-75 -4.549845E-79 -5.533119E-77 ...
2.500000E-02 -1.528953E-75 -1.866265E-73 -4.126064E-77 -5.004886E-75 ...
# ... and so on.
```

5 Sea surface output

For the sea surface, we will compare the complex wave excitation including ocean acoustic modes, coupled acoustic-elastic modes such as oceanic Rayleigh waves and tsunami generation in 30 s time increments over the simulation time (that is at $t \in [30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180, 210, 240]$ s). The files' field names and structure are explained in Tables 5, 6, and 7, and we recommend that the solution spans the sea surface for $x \in [-100, 100]$ km and $y \in [-100, 100]$ km.

Table 5: Vertical displacement of the sea surface (η ; η) in an ASCII file that contains three data fields on each line.

Field Name	Description
x [m]	Distance perpendicular to strike, that is in x-direction (E-W direction). Please refer to Section 1.3 for the coordinate convention used.
y [m]	Distance parallel to strike, that is in y-direction (N-S direction). Please refer to Section 1.3 for the coordinate convention used.
eta [m]	Vertical displacement of the sea surface.

Table 6: Sea surface output files to be uploaded for each TTPV1 and TTPV2.

File Name	Description
tsunami030s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 30 s.
tsunami060s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 60 s.
tsunami090s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 90 s.
tsunami120s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 120 s.
tsunami150s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 150 s.
tsunami180s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 180 s.
tsunami210s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 210 s.
tsunami240s	Sea surface output at a simulated time of 240 s.

Table 7: Sea surface output file structure for TTPV1 and TTPV2. The ssha ASCII file consists of three sections.

File Section	Description
File Header	<p>A series of lines, each beginning with a # symbol, that identifies the file. The following information is recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmark problem (TTPV1 or TTPV2) • Author(s) • Date • Code • Code version • Node spacing or element size • Time integration method • Simulated time • Pre- and post-processing (if applicable) • Descriptions of data columns (3 lines) • Anything else you think is relevant
Field List	<p>A single line, which lists the names of the 3 data fields, in column order, separated by spaces. It should be</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><code>x y eta</code></p> <p>(all on one line). The benchmark platform examines this line to check that your file contains the correct data fields.</p>
Sea surface output	<p>A series of lines. Each line contains 3 numbers, which gives the (x, y) coordinates of a node on the sea surface, and η.</p>

Here is an example of a sea surface vertical displacement ASCII file. This is an invented file, not real modeling data.

```
# problem = TTPV1
# author = Name Modeler
# date = 2025/01/27
# code = MyCode
# code_version = 1.2.0
# element_size (order) = 200 m (o4)
# time_integration = ADER
# simulated_time = 30 (s)
# processing = Cell data has been converted to point data to generate this file.
# Column #1 = horizontal coordinate, x-direction (m)
# Column #2 = horizontal coordinate, y-direction (m)
# Column #3 = vertical displacement of the sea surface (m)
#
x y eta
# Here is the sea surface output
-3.200000E+03 -6.400000E+03 6.797617E-03
-3.700000E+03 2.000000E+02 -1.081587E-01
7.800000E+03 -5.800000E+03 -1.336606E-02
9.400000E+03 1.100000E+04 2.051477E-01
-1.100000E+03 6.800000E+03 -3.641479E-02
1.500000E+04 4.340000E+04 -1.063315E-01
-1.800000E+03 3.140000E+04 3.629308E-02
# ... and so on.
```

6 Seafloor deformation output

We plan to compare the final (permanent) seafloor displacement for the elastic medium. The files' field names and structure are explained in Tables 8, 9, and 10, and we recommend that the solution spans the seafloor for $x \in [-100, 100]$ m and $y \in [-100, 100]$ km.

Table 8: Seafloor deformation in an ASCII file that contains three data fields on each line.

Field Name	Description
x [m]	Distance perpendicular to strike, that is in x-direction (E-W direction). Please refer to Section 1.3 for the coordinate convention used.
y [m]	Distance parallel to strike, that is in y-direction (N-S direction). Please refer to Section 1.3 for the coordinate convention used.
x-disp [m]	Horizontal displacement in x-direction, perpendicular to the fault strike. Motion eastward is positive and westward is negative.
y-disp [m]	Horizontal displacement in y-direction, parallel to the fault strike. Motion northward is positive and southward is negative.
z-disp [m]	Vertical displacement in z-direction. Please ensure that uplift is positive and subsidence is negative.

Table 9: Seafloor deformation file for TTPV1 and TTPV2.

File Name	Description
surfdef	Final deformation at the Earth's surface at the end of the simulation.

Table 10: Seafloor deformation file structure for TTPV1 and TTPV2. The ASCII file consists of three sections.

File Section	Description
File Header	<p>A series of lines, each beginning with a <code>#</code> symbol, that identifies the file. The following information is recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Benchmark problem (TTPV1 or TTPV2)• Author(s)• Date• Code• Code version• Node spacing or element size• Time integration method• Simulated time• Pre- and post-processing (if applicable)• Descriptions of data columns (5 lines)• Anything else you think is relevant
Field List	<p>A single line, which lists the names of the 3 data fields, in column order, separated by spaces. It should be</p> <pre>x y x-disp y-disp z-disp</pre> <p>(all on one line). The benchmark platform examines this line to check that your file contains the correct data fields.</p>
Surface Deformation	<p>A series of lines. Each line contains five numbers, which gives the (x, y) coordinates of a node on the Earth's surface, and the displacement of the node in the x-direction, y-direction, and z-direction.</p>

Here is an example of a seafloor deformation file. This is an invented file, not real modeling data.

```
# problem = TTPV1
# author = Name Modeler
# date = 2025/01/27
# code = MyCode
# code_version = 1.2.0
# element_size (order) = 200 m (o4)
# time_integration = ADER
# simulated_time = 240 (s)
# processing = Cell data has been converted to point data to generate this file.
# Column #1 = horizontal coordinate, x-direction (m)
# Column #2 = horizontal coordinate, y-direction (m)
# Column #3 = horizontal displacement perpendicular to strike (x-dir) (m)
# Column #4 = horizontal displacement parallel to strike (y-dir) (m)
# Column #5 = vertical displacement (z-dir) (m)
#
x y x-disp y-disp z-disp
# Here is the seafloor displacement
-3.200000E+03 -6.400000E+03 6.797617E-03 -2.903994E-02 3.074923E-01
-3.700000E+03 2.000000E+02 -1.081587E-01 -4.731012E-01 -1.241150E+00
7.800000E+03 -5.800000E+03 -1.336606E-02 -2.354464E-02 2.670004E-01
9.400000E+03 1.100000E+04 2.051477E-01 -6.435952E-01 -1.477435E+00
-1.100000E+03 6.800000E+03 -3.641479E-02 -9.962978E-01 -2.123343E+00
1.500000E+04 4.340000E+04 -1.063315E-01 -1.009014E-01 -4.282110E-01
-1.800000E+03 3.140000E+04 3.629308E-02 3.064986E-01 -1.018972E+00
# ... and so on.
```

7 On-fault stations

While not the focus of this benchmark exercise, we still want to use this opportunity and place the same 22 stations on the fault, as used for TPV36. Fig. 5 shows a plot of the on-fault station locations in the coordinate system for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Please use the same naming convention as for TPV36, shown in Table 11 below. Please upload one time-series file for each station (see Tables 12 and 13).

Figure 5: Plot of the on-fault receivers as used for TTPV1 and TTPV2.

Table 11: On-fault receivers for TTPV1 and TTPV2.

Station Name	Location
faultst000dp000	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 0.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp010	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 1.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp030	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 3.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp060	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 6.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp120	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 12.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp180	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 18.0 km down-dip.
faultst000dp240	On fault, 0.0 km along strike, 24.0 km down-dip.
faultst040dp000	On fault, 4.0 km along strike, 0.0 km down-dip.
faultst040dp030	On fault, 4.0 km along strike, 3.0 km down-dip.
faultst040dp060	On fault, 4.0 km along strike, 6.0 km down-dip.
faultst040dp120	On fault, 4.0 km along strike, 12.0 km down-dip.
faultst040dp180	On fault, 4.0 km along strike, 18.0 km down-dip.
faultst080dp000	On fault, 8.0 km along strike, 0.0 km down-dip.
faultst080dp030	On fault, 8.0 km along strike, 3.0 km down-dip.
faultst080dp060	On fault, 8.0 km along strike, 6.0 km down-dip.
faultst080dp120	On fault, 8.0 km along strike, 12.0 km down-dip.
faultst080dp180	On fault, 8.0 km along strike, 18.0 km down-dip.
faultst120dp000	On fault, 12.0 km along strike, 0.0 km down-dip.
faultst120dp030	On fault, 12.0 km along strike, 3.0 km down-dip.
faultst120dp060	On fault, 12.0 km along strike, 6.0 km down-dip.
faultst120dp120	On fault, 12.0 km along strike, 12.0 km down-dip.
faultst120dp180	On fault, 12.0 km along strike, 18.0 km down-dip.

Note: We understand that receivers at the trench (that is $w = 0$) may pose a problem. In that case, those receivers may be buried by a few centimeters, while preserving their on-fault location.

Table 12: On-fault time series data fields for TTPV1 and TTPV2. Each time series file is an ASCII file that contains 8 data fields on each line.

Field Name	Description, Units, and Sign Convention
t	Time (s).
h-slip	Horizontal slip along-strike (m).
h-slip-rate	Horizontal slip rate along-strike (m s^{-1}).
h-shear-stress	Horizontal shear stress along-strike (Pa).
v-slip	Vertical along-dip slip (m).
v-slip-rate	Vertical along-dip slip rate (m s^{-1}).
v-shear-stress	Vertical along-dip shear stress (Pa).
n-stress	Normal stress (Pa). Negative in compression.

Table 13: On-fault time series file format for TTPV1 and TTPV2. The on-fault time series file consists of three sections.

File Section	Description
File Header	<p>A series of lines, each beginning with a <code>#</code> symbol, that identifies the file. The following information is recommended:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmark problem (TTPV1 or TTPV2) • Author(s) • Date • Code • Code version • Node spacing or element size • Time integration method • Output time step • Number of output time steps in file • Station location (y,w) • Pre- and post-processing (if applicable) • Descriptions of data columns (7 lines) • Anything else you think is relevant
Field List	<p>A single line, which lists the names of the 8 data fields, in column order, separated by spaces. It should be</p> <pre style="text-align: center;">t h-slip h-slip-rate h-shear-stress v-slip v-slip-rate v-shear-stress n-stress</pre> <p>(all on one line). The benchmark platform examines this line to check that your file contains the correct data fields.</p>
Time History	<p>A series of lines. Each line contains 8 numbers, which give the data values for a single time step. The lines must appear in order of increasing time.</p>

Here is an example of an on-fault time-series file. This is an invented file, not real modeling data.

```
# problem = TTPV1
# author = Name Modeler
# date = 2025/01/27
# code = MyCode
# code_version = 1.2.0
# element_size (order) = 200 m (o4)
# time_integration = ADER
# output_time_step = 0.005
# number_output_time_steps = 2400
# location = 8.0 km along strike, 6.0 km down-dip
# processing = None
# Column #1 = Time (s)
# Column #2 = horizontal (along-strike) slip (m)
# Column #3 = horizontal (along-strike) slip rate (m/s)
# Column #4 = horizontal (along-strike) shear stress (Pa)
# Column #5 = along-dip slip (m)
# Column #6 = along-dip slip rate (m/s)
# Column #7 = along-dip shear stress (Pa)
# Column #8 = normal stress (Pa)
#
t h-slip h-slip-rate h-shear-stress v-slip v-slip-rate v-shear-stress n-stress
# There should be 8 numbers on each line, but this page is not wide enough
# to show 8 numbers on a line, so we only show the first five.
0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.000000E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
5.000000E-03 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.104040E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
1.000000E-02 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.239080E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
1.500000E-02 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.349000E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
2.000000E-02 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.440870E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
2.500000E-02 0.000000E+00 0.000000E+00 7.598240E+01 0.000000E+00 ...
# ... and so on.
```

8 Example: SeisSol-specific implementation choices

One of the codes used for this benchmark exercise is SeisSol (Uphoff et al., 2025), initially developed as highly accurate **Seismic Solver**, capable to model non-linear earthquake dynamic rupture combining coseismic frictional failure on prescribed faults with seismic wave propagation and allows coupling to tsunami generation in 3D. SeisSol is based on the **A**rbitrary high-order accurate **DER**ivative **D**iscontinuous **G**alerkin method (ADER-DG; Käser and Dumbser (2006); Dumbser and Käser (2006); Pelties et al. (2014)), has been verified in previous community benchmarks for dynamic rupture simulations (e.g., Harris et al., 2018), and uses unstructured tetrahedral meshes to incorporate complex geometries such as bathymetry and fault interface. The following details represent SeisSol specific modeling choices, but may be of use for other simulation software. Exemplary SeisSol outputs for TTPV1 and TTPV2 are shown in Fig. 6. The final moment magnitude (M_w) of TTPV1 is 7.13, while the varying bathymetry for TTPV2 affects the spatio-temporal slip distribution and consequently the final moment magnitude, generating a M_w 7.08 rupture.

8.1 Water (acoustic)

One way to combine the wave propagation in the Earth (Section 1.2.2) with the ocean (Section 1.2.3) into a fully coupled model is by treating the acoustic wave equations as a special case for the elastic wave equations. This can be achieved by setting the shear modulus (2nd Lamé’s parameter) equal to zero ($\mu = 0$). As a result, we obtain $K = \lambda = 2.25$ GPa. It is also critically important to use a mesh that places element faces along the seafloor interface, to avoid differentiating across the seafloor, because certain components of stress and velocity are discontinuous.

8.2 Element size and boundary conditions

The SeisSol solutions use an unstructured tetrahedral mesh with an element size of 200 m on the fault and 200 m in the water layer with high-order basis functions of polynomial degree $p = 4$, that is, fifth-order of accuracy in time and space for wave propagation.

SeisSol uses absorbing boundaries for the sides of the domain (i.e., the external boundaries). To account for imperfect absorbing boundary conditions at the sides of the domain and to avoid potential interactions of reflections with the benchmark results, the domain size can be chosen larger than shown in the Figs. 1, 2. For the sea surface, SeisSol implements the gravity-restoring boundary condition (Krenz et al., 2021) following the 2D implementation of Lotto and Dunham (2015).

8.3 Off-fault station details

8.3.1 Elastic: seafloor

TTPV1

Modelers should ensure 34 off-fault receivers in TTPV1 are located within the elastic domain. One possibility is “burying” receiver locations, e.g., 10 cm beneath the seafloor (that is subtracting 0.1 m from the depth z). This will introduce an error of order of the burial depth, but this error is most likely very small given the length scales over which fields vary in these benchmark problems. In the SeisSol solutions, the 34 off-fault receivers have a depth of $z = -0.1$ m.

TTPV2

Recall that the bathymetry of TTPV2 varies with distance perpendicular to the fault trace. In case of burying the 34 off-fault receivers for the elastic domain by 10 cm beneath the seafloor, the 13 receivers westward (seaward) of the trench have a depth of $z = -0.1$ m, while the other 21 receivers to the east (landwards) should have a depth of $z = h * [1 - \exp(-x/L)] - 0.1$ m (see Section 1.3.2).

8.3.2 Acoustic: seafloor

TTPV1

One option to ensure 34 off-fault receivers in TTPV1 are located within the acoustic domain (just above the seafloor within the water), is “lifting” them by 10 cm (that is adding 0.1 m to the depth z). As a result, in the SeisSol solution, the 34 off-fault receivers have a depth of $z = 0.1$ m.

TTPV2

Recall that the bathymetry of TTPV2 varies with distance perpendicular to the fault trace. Lifting the 34 off-fault receivers for the elastic domain by 10 cm w.r.t the seafloor means that the 13 receivers westward (seaward) of the trench have a depth of $z = 0.1$ m, while the other 21 receivers to the east (landwards) should have a depth of $z = h * [1 - \exp(-x/L)] + 0.1$ m (see Section 1.3.2).

8.3.3 Acoustic: sea surface

TTPV1

34 off-fault receivers should also be placed on or near the sea surface. One option is placing the receivers 10 cm beneath the sea surface. In the SeisSol solution, we use the same x and y coordinates as chosen in the previous sections, with the depth of the 34 off-fault receivers for TTPV1 being $z = 999.9$ m.

TTPV2

Recall that the sea surface for TTPV2 is at 3 km (positive z-direction). Burying the 34 off-fault receivers by 10 cm each would place them at a depth $z = 2999.9$ m. Other than that, use the same x and y coordinates as chosen in the previous sections.

8.4 Pressure output (Acoustic: seafloor & sea surface)

If the ocean is treated as a special case of an elastic solid, as described earlier, the Eulerian pressure perturbation p' about the hydrostatic rest state (Column #8 in the off-fault time series for the receivers in the acoustic medium) can be inferred from the stress change tensor $\sigma_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}^0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$ via

$$p' = -\frac{1}{3}(\sigma_{ii} - \sigma_{ii}^0). \quad (23)$$

The Lagrangian pressure perturbation Δp (Column #9 in the off-fault time series for the receivers in the acoustic medium) can be calculated using

$$\Delta p = p' - \rho g u_z, \quad (24)$$

where p' is the pressure perturbation from Eq. 23 and ρ is the density prescribed in the water layer (Section 2) and u_z is the vertical displacement (positive up).

Figure 6: (a) Vertical seafloor deformation of TTPV1 and TTPV2 from SeisSol simulations. (b) Simulated vertical displacement of the sea surface at $t = 90$ s for TTPV1 and TTPV2 from SeisSol simulations together with a cross section at $y = 0$.

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